

5600+ Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

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*The whole work as pdf files are available at author's
web-site: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=11781>*

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of order 16 based on **equal width magic rectangles**. These are magic rectangles of type 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 , etc. Alternatively, we can write it as $2 \times n$, where n is the length of magic rectangle. Magic squares constructed based on **equal width magic rectangles**, we call as **striped magic squares**. For the **striped** magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 18 refer the author's work [94, 95, 96]. The previous work was only with 2104 **striped magic squares** of order 16, while this version is with 5641 **striped magic squares**. The whole work with 5641 **striped magic squares** is available as **pdf file** at author's web-site. The link is as given above.*

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1 Introduction

Let's understand first about **striped magic rectangles**, i.e., **equal width magic rectangles**. These are of orders 2×4 , 2×4 , 2×4 , etc. It is based on following two ideas recently, developed by the author:

- (i) Striped Bordered Double Digits Magic Rectangles.
- (ii) Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles.

The above two items are not known in the literature of magic squares. Let's understand one by one.

1.1 Bordered Double Digits Magic Rectangles

Here we shall bring double digits bordered magic rectangles. See below few examples.

Example 1.1. Below is an example of **double digit bordered magic rectangle** of order 6×14 :

11	8	7	71	5	70	69	73	84	23	26	63	13	72	595
74	77	78	14	80	15	16	12	1	62	59	22	76	9	595
66	19	52	42	50	40	41	47	34	37	36	46	24	61	595
65	20	33	43	35	45	44	38	51	48	49	39	57	28	595
10	75	81	27	68	67	21	53	30	3	25	2	79	54	595
29	56	4	58	17	18	64	32	55	82	60	83	6	31	595
255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255

The magic rectangle of width 2 are of equal sums. See below:

11	8	7	71	5	70	69	73	84	23	26	63	510
74	77	78	14	80	15	16	12	1	62	59	22	510
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	
81	27	68	67	21	53	30	3	25	2	79	54	510
4	58	17	18	64	32	55	82	60	83	6	31	510
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	
			13	72	85		66	19	85			
			76	9	85		65	20	85			
			24	61	85		10	75	85			
			57	28	85		29	56	85			
			170	170			170	170				

Example 1.2. Below is an another example of **double digit bordered magic rectangle** of order 10×12 :

The sums are as follows:

71	69	72	5	6	67	70	3	68	2	1	76	510	12	73	85	58	27	85
14	16	13	80	79	18	15	82	17	83	84	9	510	74	11	85	60	25	85
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85		4	81	85	29	56	85
													78	7	85	23	62	85
26	66	32	64	65	31	22	28	61	30			425	77	8	85	170	170	
59	19	53	21	20	54	63	57	24	55			425	10	75	85			
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85			255	255				
52	47	40	37	42	36	41	50	34	46			425						
33	38	45	48	43	49	44	35	51	39			425						
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85								

Example 1.4. Below is an example of another **striped cornered magic rectangle** of order 10×12 :

59	61	64	58	68	53	73	48	86	35	18	103	726
62	60	57	63	50	71	76	45	24	97	108	13	726
72	65	54	51	69	52	46	75	22	99	8	113	726
49	56	67	70	55	66	41	80	98	23	104	17	726
74	84	81	39	42	43	44	77	29	92	102	19	726
47	37	40	82	79	78	83	38	34	87	15	106	726
90	26	33	96	94	32	85	28	91	30	115	6	726
31	95	88	25	27	89	36	93	100	21	114	7	726
109	116	2	118	1	4	112	16	107	20	11	110	726
12	5	119	3	120	117	9	105	14	101	10	111	726
605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	

The sums are as follows:

109	116	2	118	1	4	112	16	107	20	605	18	103	121	86	35	121	73	48	121	68	53	121
12	5	119	3	120	117	9	105	14	101	605	108	13	121	24	97	121	76	45	121	50	71	121
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	8	113	121	22	99	121	46	75	121	69	52	121
											104	17	121	98	23	121	41	80	121	55	66	121
90	26	33	96	94	32	85	28	484	102	19	121	29	92	121	44	77	121	242	242			
31	95	88	25	27	89	36	93	484	15	106	121	34	87	121	83	38	121					
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121		115	6	121	91	30	121	363	363						
									114	7	121	100	21	121								
74	84	81	39	42	43	363	11	110	121	484	484											
47	37	40	82	79	78	363	10	111	121													
121	121	121	121	121	121		605	605														
72	65	54	51	242	59	61	64	58	242													
49	56	67	70	242	62	60	57	63	242													
121	121	121	121		121	121	121	121														

1.3 Stripes of Equal Width

Whole the work is based on equal width magic rectangles of order $2 \times n$, where $n = 4, 6, \dots, 20$. These are as follows:

1	254 255 1 4 5 251 250 8 9 247 246 12 242 243 13 16	2056
	3 2 256 253 252 6 7 249 248 10 11 245 15 14 244 241	2056
	257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257	
2	247 256 15 38 11 228 232 36 2 13 218 211 53 239	1799
	10 1 242 219 246 29 25 221 255 244 39 46 204 18	1799
	257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257	
3	60 57 199 198 61 195 191 64 65 68 194 190	1542
	197 200 58 59 196 62 66 193 192 189 63 67	1542
	257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257	
4	173 72 59 88 184 68 92 186 193 170	1285
	84 185 198 169 73 189 165 71 64 87	1285
	257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257	
5	104 97 159 157 156 154 102 99	1028
	153 160 98 100 101 103 155 158	1028
	257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257 257	
6	108 153 152 100 98 160	771
	149 104 105 157 159 97	771
	257 257 257 257 257 257	
7	121 135 134 124	514
	136 122 123 133	514
	257 257 257 257	

From the above example, we observe that in the all the case, the width is always 401. The length changes according to the order of magic rectangle.

2 Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

In this work there are total 5641 **striped magic squares** of order 16. The whole work is divided in 14 parts as subsections.

2.1 Part 1: General, Cornered and Double Digits Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16 made in a general way. Some of them include **striped cornered**, **striped double digits bordered**, etc. Below are few

examples:

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	247	256	15	38	11	228	232	36	2	13	218	211	53	239	234	23	2056
	10	1	242	219	246	29	25	221	255	244	39	46	204	18	7	250	2056
	43	214	173	72	59	88	184	68	92	186	193	170	93	164	216	41	2056
	8	249	84	185	198	169	73	189	165	71	64	87	95	162	12	245	2056
	210	47	166	91	108	153	152	100	98	160	142	115	197	60	3	254	2056
	222	35	182	75	149	104	105	157	159	97	155	102	79	178	252	5	2056
	33	224	85	172	110	147	135	122	130	127	143	114	81	176	240	17	2056
	26	231	187	70	146	111	121	136	128	129	101	156	82	175	16	241	2056
	207	50	199	58	144	113	134	123	125	132	112	145	183	74	54	203	2056
	56	201	89	168	158	99	124	133	131	126	118	139	200	57	51	206	2056
	236	21	180	77	107	150	141	148	120	119	140	103	94	163	209	48	2056
	30	227	61	196	106	151	116	109	137	138	117	154	181	76	213	44	2056
	205	52	69	188	78	192	194	96	195	86	80	83	90	191	55	202	2056
	248	9	67	190	179	65	63	161	62	171	177	174	167	66	237	20	2056
	24	233	27	253	225	235	31	45	34	19	14	220	229	42	217	208	2056
	251	6	230	4	32	22	226	212	223	238	243	37	28	215	40	49	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	254	255	1	4	5	251	250	8	9	247	246	12	242	243	13	16	2056
	3	2	256	253	252	6	7	249	248	10	11	245	15	14	244	241	2056
	53	204	60	57	199	198	61	195	191	64	65	68	194	190	17	240	2056
	203	54	197	200	58	59	196	62	66	193	192	189	63	67	239	18	2056
	202	55	93	164	104	97	159	157	156	154	102	99	69	188	238	19	2056
	56	201	163	94	153	160	98	100	101	103	155	158	187	70	20	237	2056
	49	208	162	95	113	144	121	136	125	132	117	140	186	71	21	236	2056
	207	50	96	161	116	141	135	122	131	126	120	137	72	185	235	22	2056
	206	51	89	168	143	114	134	123	130	127	139	118	73	184	234	23	2056
	52	205	167	90	142	115	124	133	128	129	138	119	183	74	24	233	2056
	45	212	166	91	105	112	107	148	149	110	151	146	182	75	25	232	2056
	211	46	92	165	152	145	150	109	108	147	106	111	76	181	231	26	2056
	210	47	171	175	88	85	81	170	174	84	178	179	77	80	230	27	2056
	48	209	86	82	169	172	176	87	83	173	79	78	180	177	28	229	2056
	44	41	214	215	37	219	218	40	33	223	222	36	29	32	227	226	2056
	213	216	43	42	220	38	39	217	224	34	35	221	228	225	30	31	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				@IJTANEJA		2056	
	125	131	130	128	117	140	113	144	89	168	81	176	47	210	33	224	2056
	132	126	127	129	139	118	143	114	167	90	175	82	209	48	43	214	2056
	121	135	134	124	138	119	142	115	91	166	83	174	45	212	35	222	2056
	136	122	123	133	120	137	116	141	165	92	173	84	211	46	221	36	2056
	105	151	107	149	148	110	146	112	164	93	172	85	208	49	220	37	2056
	152	106	150	108	109	147	111	145	94	163	86	171	207	50	219	38	2056
	97	159	99	157	156	154	102	104	162	95	170	87	51	206	39	218	2056
	160	98	158	100	101	103	155	153	96	161	88	169	52	205	40	217	2056
	69	187	71	185	184	183	75	76	77	179	79	177	53	204	41	216	2056
	188	70	186	72	73	74	182	181	180	78	178	80	203	54	215	42	2056
	57	199	59	197	196	195	63	64	65	191	67	189	55	202	223	34	2056
	200	58	198	60	61	62	194	193	192	66	190	68	201	56	213	44	2056
	17	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	27	228	229	30	226	32	2056
	240	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	230	29	28	227	31	225	2056
	253	11	3	255	252	6	250	8	9	247	242	245	244	14	1	16	2056
	4	246	254	2	5	251	7	249	248	10	15	12	13	243	256	241	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

6	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				@IJTANEJA		2056	
	22	237	29	47	35	223	61	212	231	191	214	50	220	27	234	23	2056
	235	20	228	210	222	34	196	45	26	66	43	207	37	230	203	54	2056
	204	53	91	99	87	80	188	74	176	174	154	162	187	70	24	233	2056
	211	46	166	158	170	177	69	183	81	83	103	95	186	71	55	202	2056
	58	199	157	100	115	152	143	120	123	118	124	133	160	97	21	236	2056
	65	192	102	155	142	105	114	137	134	139	122	135	88	169	25	232	2056
	206	51	78	179	150	107	130	128	131	125	149	108	164	93	226	31	2056
	17	240	104	153	148	109	127	129	126	132	119	138	72	185	225	32	2056
	224	33	171	86	106	151	136	116	117	144	112	146	96	161	56	201	2056
	41	216	165	92	110	147	121	141	140	113	145	111	75	182	44	213	2056
	59	198	178	79	101	167	172	94	84	181	82	159	77	168	229	28	2056
	215	42	73	184	156	90	85	163	173	76	175	98	180	89	200	57	2056
	194	63	227	219	40	195	67	218	19	49	18	68	193	60	205	221	2056
	48	209	30	38	217	62	190	39	238	208	239	189	64	197	52	36	2056
	1	3	255	253	252	6	250	8	9	247	11	242	244	14	245	16	2056
	256	254	2	4	5	251	7	249	248	10	246	15	13	243	12	241	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 6 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.2 Part 2: Based on Two Magic Rectangles of Order 2×16

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16 a such a way that these two magic rectangles are either at beginning or at the end. The middle part are magic rectangles of order 12×16 resulting in **striped magic squares** of order 16. See below few examples.

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	1	255	3	253	252	14	250	8	9	247	11	245	244	242	6	16	2056
	256	2	254	4	5	243	7	249	248	10	246	12	13	15	251	241	2056
	49	208	57	200	73	184	77	180	125	132	121	136	105	152	97	160	2056
	207	50	199	58	183	74	179	78	131	126	135	122	151	106	159	98	2056
	51	206	59	198	182	75	178	79	130	127	134	123	107	150	99	158	2056
	205	52	197	60	76	181	80	177	128	129	124	133	149	108	157	100	2056
	204	53	196	61	69	187	186	72	117	139	138	120	148	109	156	101	2056
	54	203	62	195	188	70	71	185	140	118	119	137	110	147	102	155	2056
	202	55	194	63	65	191	190	68	113	143	142	116	146	111	154	103	2056
	56	201	64	193	192	66	67	189	144	114	115	141	112	145	104	153	2056
	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	89	167	91	165	164	94	162	96	2056
	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	168	90	166	92	93	163	95	161	2056
	221	223	35	33	220	38	218	40	81	175	83	173	172	86	170	88	2056
	36	34	222	224	37	219	39	217	176	82	174	84	85	171	87	169	2056
	17	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	27	229	228	30	226	32	2056
	240	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	230	28	29	227	31	225	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	1	255	3	253	252	6	250	8	9	247	11	245	242	16	244	14	2056
	256	2	254	4	5	251	7	249	248	10	246	12	15	241	13	243	2056
	184	73	190	191	58	75	33	224	45	212	148	109	154	155	94	111	2056
	78	179	67	66	199	182	223	34	211	46	144	113	103	102	163	146	2056
	180	77	165	92	188	69	35	222	47	210	112	145	129	128	152	105	2056
	194	63	89	168	74	183	221	36	209	48	158	99	125	132	110	147	2056
	64	193	90	167	177	80	220	37	208	49	101	156	126	131	141	116	2056
	176	81	166	91	83	174	219	38	207	50	140	117	130	127	119	138	2056
	76	181	172	85	59	198	39	218	51	206	114	143	136	121	95	162	2056
	82	175	87	170	187	70	40	217	52	205	118	139	123	134	151	106	2056
	65	192	171	86	84	173	41	216	53	204	100	157	135	122	120	137	2056
	186	71	88	169	60	197	215	42	203	54	150	107	124	133	96	161	2056
	57	72	196	189	195	62	43	214	55	202	108	93	153	160	159	98	2056
	200	185	61	68	178	79	213	44	201	56	149	164	104	97	142	115	2056
	25	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	17	231	27	229	226	32	228	30	2056
	232	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	240	26	230	28	31	225	29	227	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

40	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	3	255	1	253	252	6	242	8	9	247	11	245	244	14	250	16	2056
	254	2	256	4	5	251	15	249	248	10	246	12	13	243	7	241	2056
	190	67	221	196	49	204	66	194	39	59	93	164	113	144	121	136	2056
	58	199	36	61	208	53	191	63	218	198	163	94	143	114	135	122	2056
	68	189	71	186	181	171	74	88	192	65	95	162	115	142	123	134	2056
	38	219	177	80	76	86	183	169	57	200	161	96	141	116	133	124	2056
	197	60	188	69	90	167	182	75	193	64	160	97	140	117	132	125	2056
	207	50	175	82	168	89	70	187	47	210	159	98	118	139	126	131	2056
	217	40	77	180	165	92	184	73	215	42	99	158	138	119	130	127	2056
	56	201	83	174	91	166	72	185	212	45	100	157	120	137	128	129	2056
	51	206	85	81	170	178	179	78	46	211	101	156	109	147	146	112	2056
	203	54	172	176	87	79	84	173	220	37	155	102	148	110	111	145	2056
	223	202	43	209	52	44	33	222	41	216	103	154	105	151	150	108	2056
	34	55	214	48	205	213	224	35	62	195	153	104	152	106	107	149	2056
	17	239	228	30	236	22	234	19	25	231	27	229	237	32	226	24	2056
	240	18	29	227	21	235	23	238	232	26	230	28	20	225	31	233	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

73	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	77	180	73	184	57	200	49	208	81	175	83	173	172	86	170	88	2056	
	80	177	182	75	199	58	207	50	176	82	174	84	85	171	87	169	2056	
	178	79	183	74	59	198	51	206	89	167	91	165	162	96	164	94	2056	
	179	78	76	181	197	60	205	52	168	90	166	92	95	161	93	163	2056	
	69	187	186	72	196	61	204	53	97	160	148	109	113	143	142	116	2056	
	188	70	71	185	62	195	54	203	159	98	110	147	144	114	115	141	2056	
	65	191	190	68	194	63	202	55	99	158	107	150	117	139	138	120	2056	
	192	66	67	189	64	193	56	201	157	100	149	108	140	118	119	137	2056	
	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	156	101	151	106	121	136	125	132	2056	
	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	154	103	105	152	135	122	131	126	2056	
	33	223	35	221	220	38	218	40	102	155	146	111	134	123	130	127	2056	
	224	34	222	36	37	219	39	217	104	153	112	145	124	133	128	129	2056	
	1	255	3	253	252	6	250	8	9	247	11	245	16	242	14	244	2056	
	256	2	254	4	5	251	7	249	248	10	246	12	241	15	243	13	2056	
	17	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	27	229	228	30	32	226	2056	
	240	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	230	28	29	227	225	31	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

There are total 126 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.3 Part 3: Based on Two Magic Rectangles of Order 6×8 and 8x10

This part brings some striped magic squares of order 16 constructed with the help of four magic rectangle, where two of them are of orders 6 × 8 and another two are of orders 10 × 8. See below few examples

250	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	146	101	162	145	109	108	155	102	80	177	182	75	57	200	207	50	2056	
	111	156	95	112	148	149	158	99	179	78	183	74	199	58	202	55	2056	
	147	110	140	118	137	119	91	166	178	79	76	181	59	198	51	206	2056	
	153	104	117	139	120	138	105	152	77	180	73	184	197	60	49	208	2056	
	164	93	141	144	115	114	103	154	69	72	186	187	194	63	204	53	2056	
	107	150	116	113	142	143	159	98	188	185	71	70	64	193	54	203	2056	
	94	163	89	167	157	96	97	165	65	191	190	68	196	61	205	52	2056	
	106	151	168	90	100	161	160	92	192	66	67	189	62	195	56	201	2056	
	121	135	123	133	132	126	130	128	215	41	210	213	212	46	43	48	2056	
	136	122	134	124	125	131	127	129	42	216	47	44	45	211	214	209	2056	
	9	248	242	15	17	238	239	20	218	40	37	219	84	173	170	87	2056	
	247	10	13	244	240	19	18	237	39	217	220	38	81	176	85	172	2056	
	12	245	243	14	21	235	234	24	33	223	222	36	175	82	88	169	2056	
	246	11	16	241	236	22	23	233	224	34	35	221	174	83	171	86	2056	
	255	3	1	253	252	6	250	8	228	231	229	226	27	30	32	25	2056	
	2	254	256	4	5	251	7	249	29	26	28	31	230	227	225	232	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

600	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	100	161	160	92	90	168	151	106	204	53	196	61	73	184	178	79	2056	
	157	96	97	165	167	89	163	94	202	55	59	198	183	74	179	78	2056	
	98	159	143	142	113	116	150	107	51	206	62	195	182	75	77	180	2056	
	154	103	114	115	144	141	93	164	205	52	194	63	76	181	80	177	2056	
	152	105	138	120	139	117	104	153	207	50	199	58	69	187	186	72	2056	
	166	91	119	137	118	140	110	147	54	203	57	200	188	70	71	185	2056	
	99	158	148	156	112	95	149	111	49	208	197	60	65	191	190	68	2056	
	102	155	109	101	145	162	108	146	56	201	64	193	192	66	67	189	2056	
	121	135	123	133	130	126	132	128	215	43	210	213	212	46	48	41	2056	
	136	122	134	124	127	131	125	129	42	214	47	44	45	211	209	216	2056	
	252	6	250	253	1	8	255	3	33	224	37	220	88	171	170	85	2056	
	5	251	7	4	256	249	2	254	223	34	219	38	169	86	87	172	2056	
	9	247	12	246	17	240	21	236	222	35	218	39	84	81	175	174	2056	
	248	10	245	11	239	18	235	22	36	221	40	217	173	176	82	83	2056	
	13	16	242	243	238	19	234	23	228	231	229	226	27	30	32	25	2056	
	244	241	15	14	20	237	24	233	29	26	28	31	230	227	225	232	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

872	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				@IJTANEJA	2056						
157	160	98	99	96	161	138	119	215	210	43	213	212	46	41	48	2056	
100	97	159	158	94	163	120	137	42	47	214	44	45	211	216	209	2056	
149	107	106	152	162	95	118	139	65	68	190	191	57	200	49	208	2056	
108	150	151	105	167	90	143	114	192	189	67	66	59	198	204	53	2056	
156	102	103	153	164	93	140	117	69	187	186	72	196	61	51	206	2056	
101	155	154	104	89	168	113	144	188	70	71	185	199	58	205	52	2056	
146	109	147	112	165	92	115	142	77	180	73	184	197	60	56	201	2056	
111	148	110	145	91	166	141	116	179	78	183	74	62	195	54	203	2056	
121	135	123	133	132	126	130	128	178	79	182	75	194	63	207	50	2056	
136	122	134	124	125	131	127	129	80	177	76	181	64	193	202	55	2056	
9	248	13	244	17	20	238	239	218	40	37	219	174	83	170	87	2056	
247	10	16	241	240	237	19	18	39	217	220	38	81	176	85	172	2056	
12	245	242	15	21	235	234	24	33	223	222	36	175	82	88	169	2056	
246	11	243	14	236	22	23	233	224	34	35	221	84	173	171	86	2056	
252	253	1	250	8	6	255	3	228	229	231	226	27	30	25	32	2056	
5	4	256	7	249	251	2	254	29	28	26	31	230	227	232	225	2056	
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

1352	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				@IJTANEJA	2056						
106	94	107	164	153	147	111	146	215	41	43	210	212	46	213	48	2056	
151	163	150	93	104	110	156	101	42	216	214	47	45	211	44	209	2056	
168	89	116	141	117	140	95	162	49	208	197	60	65	68	190	191	2056	
90	167	113	144	139	118	112	145	56	201	64	193	192	189	67	66	2056	
100	157	142	115	120	137	148	109	51	206	57	200	69	187	186	72	2056	
161	96	143	114	138	119	149	108	54	203	199	58	188	70	71	185	2056	
160	97	159	103	105	91	158	155	202	55	196	61	73	184	178	79	2056	
92	165	98	154	152	166	99	102	207	50	62	195	183	74	179	78	2056	
128	130	123	133	132	126	121	135	204	53	194	63	182	75	77	180	2056	
129	127	134	124	125	131	136	122	205	52	59	198	76	181	80	177	2056	
33	223	36	222	246	11	5	252	17	240	24	233	85	88	171	170	2056	
224	34	221	35	247	10	251	6	239	18	21	236	172	169	86	87	2056	
230	27	29	228	9	248	250	7	238	19	234	23	81	176	40	217	2056	
231	26	32	225	12	245	8	249	20	237	235	22	84	173	37	220	2056	
28	229	227	30	1	255	254	4	13	243	242	16	175	82	219	38	2056	
25	232	226	31	256	2	3	253	244	14	15	241	174	83	218	39	2056	
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 1232 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.4 Part 4: Based on Magic Rectangles of Different Orders

This part is very much similar to part 3. See below few examples.

1369	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	96	161	105	108	151	150	97	160	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056
	89	168	152	149	106	107	104	153	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056
	167	90	113	144	117	140	99	158	191	66	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056
	165	92	143	114	139	118	156	101	205	52	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056
	164	93	142	115	138	119	157	100	215	42	73	182	183	76	49	208	2056
	162	95	116	141	120	137	102	155	62	195	184	75	74	181	213	44	2056
	94	163	109	112	147	146	159	98	47	210	77	179	178	80	41	216	2056
	91	166	148	145	110	111	154	103	60	197	180	78	79	177	203	54	2056
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	65	51	202	214	45	194	190	67	2056
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	192	206	55	43	212	63	207	50	2056
	252	6	1	253	255	3	250	8	226	231	25	32	27	30	228	229	2056
	5	251	256	4	2	254	7	249	31	26	232	225	230	227	29	28	2056
	246	11	16	241	17	240	21	236	33	224	37	220	84	173	170	87	2056
	247	10	13	244	239	18	235	22	223	34	219	38	174	83	85	172	2056
	12	245	242	15	238	19	234	23	222	35	218	39	175	82	171	86	2056
	9	248	243	14	20	237	24	233	36	221	40	217	81	176	88	169	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

1432	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056										
	100	158	159	97	96	161	101	156	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056
	157	99	98	160	162	95	155	102	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056
	89	167	166	92	163	94	154	103	191	66	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056
	168	90	91	165	93	164	104	153	205	52	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056
	113	144	108	149	112	146	147	109	215	42	73	182	183	76	49	208	2056
	143	114	150	107	145	111	110	148	62	195	184	75	74	181	213	44	2056
	142	115	151	106	117	139	138	120	47	210	77	179	178	80	41	216	2056
	116	141	105	152	140	118	119	137	60	197	180	78	79	177	203	54	2056
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	45	51	214	202	65	194	190	67	2056
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	212	206	43	55	192	63	207	50	2056
	252	6	1	253	255	3	250	8	33	224	219	38	170	87	175	82	2056
	5	251	256	4	2	254	7	249	223	34	218	39	171	86	174	83	2056
	246	11	16	241	17	240	21	236	222	35	37	220	88	169	84	173	2056
	247	10	13	244	239	18	235	22	36	221	40	217	85	172	81	176	2056
	12	245	242	15	238	19	234	23	228	229	231	226	27	25	32	30	2056
	9	248	243	14	20	237	24	233	29	28	26	31	230	232	225	227	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

1482	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056										
	146	101	162	145	109	108	155	102	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056
	111	156	95	112	148	149	158	99	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056
	147	110	140	118	137	119	91	166	191	66	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056
	153	104	117	139	120	138	105	152	205	52	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056
	164	93	141	144	115	114	103	154	215	42	73	182	183	76	49	208	2056
	107	150	116	113	142	143	159	98	62	195	184	75	74	181	213	44	2056
	94	163	89	167	157	96	97	165	47	210	77	179	178	80	41	216	2056
	106	151	168	90	100	161	160	92	60	197	180	78	79	177	203	54	2056
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	45	51	202	214	65	194	190	67	2056
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	212	206	55	43	192	63	207	50	2056
	9	248	242	15	17	238	239	20	37	40	219	218	170	87	175	82	2056
	247	10	13	244	240	19	18	237	220	217	38	39	171	86	174	83	2056
	12	245	243	14	21	235	234	24	33	223	222	36	88	169	84	173	2056
	246	11	16	241	236	22	23	233	224	34	35	221	85	172	81	176	2056
	255	3	1	253	252	6	250	8	228	229	231	226	27	25	32	30	2056
	2	254	256	4	5	251	7	249	29	28	26	31	230	232	225	227	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

1727	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://numbers-magic.com/		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		@IJTANEJA	2056							
111	146	101	156	108	149	100	157	200	57	53	58	211	189	59	201	2056
148	109	155	102	150	107	97	160	191	66	204	199	46	68	198	56	2056
110	147	154	103	151	106	159	98	48	209	69	72	187	186	64	193	2056
145	112	104	153	105	152	158	99	205	52	188	185	70	71	61	196	2056
91	165	89	164	167	162	94	96	215	42	76	183	73	182	49	208	2056
166	92	168	93	90	95	163	161	62	195	181	74	184	75	41	216	2056
141	115	113	140	143	118	120	138	60	197	77	179	178	80	213	44	2056
116	142	144	117	114	139	137	119	47	210	180	78	79	177	203	54	2056
130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	65	45	202	214	51	194	190	67	2056
127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	192	212	55	43	206	63	207	50	2056
25	231	230	28	245	16	237	252	3	18	242	15	37	219	218	40	2056
232	26	27	229	12	241	20	5	254	239	255	2	220	38	39	217	2056
226	31	36	221	251	6	236	23	233	22	7	250	84	173	85	172	2056
29	228	222	35	14	243	21	234	24	235	10	247	174	83	170	87	2056
227	30	33	224	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	81	176	171	86	2056
32	225	223	34	1	256	246	4	19	249	240	13	175	82	88	169	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 396 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [97].

2.5 Part 5: Based on Magic Rectangles of Different Orders

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is also very much similar to parts 3 and 4. See below few examples.

1896	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	96	89	167	165	164	162	94	91	215	41	43	213	212	46	210	48	2056		
	161	168	90	92	93	95	163	166	42	216	214	44	45	211	47	209	2056		
	105	152	113	144	117	140	109	148	49	208	197	60	65	68	190	191	2056		
	108	149	143	114	139	118	112	145	56	201	64	193	192	189	67	66	2056		
	151	106	142	115	138	119	147	110	51	206	57	200	69	187	186	72	2056		
	150	107	116	141	120	137	146	111	54	203	199	58	188	70	71	185	2056		
	97	104	99	156	157	102	159	154	202	55	196	61	73	184	178	79	2056		
	160	153	158	101	100	155	98	103	207	50	62	195	183	74	179	78	2056		
	128	130	123	133	132	126	121	135	205	52	194	63	182	75	77	180	2056		
	129	127	134	124	125	131	136	122	204	53	59	198	76	181	80	177	2056		
	3	252	16	245	237	18	7	250	229	231	25	30	228	27	226	32	2056		
	254	5	241	12	20	239	242	15	28	26	232	227	29	230	31	225	2056		
	1	256	22	236	23	233	255	2	33	224	37	220	175	82	171	86	2056		
	14	243	235	21	234	24	10	247	223	34	219	38	174	83	170	87	2056		
	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	222	35	218	39	81	176	88	169	2056		
	251	6	246	4	19	249	240	13	36	221	40	217	84	173	85	172	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056		

1932	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	116	142	144	117	114	139	137	119	215	41	43	213	212	46	210	48	2056		
	141	115	113	140	143	118	120	138	42	216	214	44	45	211	47	209	2056		
	166	92	168	93	90	95	163	161	49	208	197	60	65	68	190	191	2056		
	91	165	89	164	167	162	94	96	56	201	64	193	192	189	67	66	2056		
	156	102	103	153	105	152	158	99	51	206	57	200	69	187	186	72	2056		
	101	155	154	104	151	106	159	98	54	203	199	58	188	70	71	185	2056		
	146	109	147	112	150	107	97	160	202	55	196	61	73	184	178	79	2056		
	111	148	110	145	108	149	100	157	207	50	62	195	183	74	179	78	2056		
	128	130	123	133	132	126	121	135	205	52	194	63	182	75	77	180	2056		
	129	127	134	124	125	131	136	122	204	53	59	198	76	181	80	177	2056		
	3	252	16	245	237	18	7	250	229	231	25	30	228	27	226	32	2056		
	254	5	241	12	20	239	242	15	28	26	232	227	29	230	31	225	2056		
	1	256	22	236	23	233	255	2	33	224	37	220	175	174	81	84	2056		
	14	243	235	21	234	24	10	247	223	34	219	38	82	83	176	173	2056		
	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	222	35	218	39	171	170	88	85	2056		
	251	6	246	4	19	249	240	13	36	221	40	217	86	87	169	172	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056		

2209	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056
102	99	166	152	154	98	165	92	204	53	196	61	76	181	77	180	2056
155	158	91	105	103	159	97	160	202	55	59	198	183	74	80	177	2056
108	149	119	138	114	143	96	161	51	206	62	195	182	75	178	79	2056
109	148	137	120	115	142	157	100	205	52	199	58	73	184	179	78	2056
145	112	118	139	144	113	167	90	207	50	194	63	69	187	186	72	2056
162	95	140	117	141	116	89	168	54	203	64	193	188	70	71	185	2056
101	156	110	104	93	150	163	151	49	208	197	60	65	191	190	68	2056
146	111	147	153	164	107	94	106	56	201	57	200	192	66	67	189	2056
132	135	123	133	130	126	121	128	210	46	215	213	212	43	48	41	2056
125	122	134	124	127	131	136	129	47	211	42	44	45	214	209	216	2056
252	6	3	253	250	8	255	1	40	173	27	228	82	221	31	226	2056
5	251	254	4	7	249	2	256	217	84	230	29	175	36	218	39	2056
9	248	13	244	17	240	21	236	227	30	172	87	169	86	231	26	2056
247	10	243	14	239	18	235	22	38	219	85	170	88	171	34	223	2056
12	245	242	15	238	19	234	23	224	33	35	229	81	32	174	220	2056
246	11	16	241	20	237	24	233	25	232	222	28	176	225	83	37	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

2479	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056
157	100	149	108	145	110	148	111	80	177	182	75	57	200	207	50	2056
160	97	107	150	112	147	109	146	179	78	183	74	199	58	202	55	2056
98	159	106	151	104	154	155	101	178	79	76	181	59	198	51	206	2056
99	158	152	105	153	103	102	156	77	180	73	184	196	61	49	208	2056
96	94	162	167	164	89	165	91	69	72	186	187	194	63	204	53	2056
161	163	95	90	93	168	92	166	188	185	71	70	64	193	54	203	2056
138	120	118	143	140	113	115	141	65	190	191	68	197	60	205	52	2056
119	137	139	114	117	144	142	116	192	67	66	189	62	195	56	201	2056
130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	215	41	210	213	212	46	43	48	2056
127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	42	216	47	44	45	211	214	209	2056
25	232	226	31	252	3	237	245	16	18	10	247	84	173	37	220	2056
231	26	32	225	5	254	20	12	241	239	7	250	174	83	219	38	2056
230	27	227	30	251	6	236	23	233	22	255	2	81	176	218	39	2056
28	229	29	228	14	243	21	234	24	235	242	15	175	82	40	217	2056
36	222	33	223	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	85	170	88	171	2056
221	35	224	34	1	256	246	4	19	249	240	13	172	87	169	86	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 792 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.6 Part 6: Based on Magic Rectangles of Different Orders

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is also very much similar to parts 3, 4 and 5. See below few examples.

2557	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	154	103	105	152	121	136	131	126	2056
	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	159	98	151	106	135	122	125	132	2056
	65	191	190	68	57	200	49	208	99	158	107	150	134	123	130	127	2056
	192	66	67	189	197	60	207	50	157	100	149	108	124	133	128	129	2056
	69	187	186	72	59	198	51	206	156	101	148	109	117	139	138	120	2056
	188	70	71	185	199	58	205	52	102	155	112	145	140	118	119	137	2056
	77	180	73	184	196	61	204	53	104	153	146	111	113	143	142	116	2056
	179	78	183	74	62	195	54	203	97	160	110	147	144	114	115	141	2056
	178	79	182	75	194	63	202	55	89	96	91	165	164	94	162	167	2056
	80	177	76	181	64	193	56	201	168	161	166	92	93	163	95	90	2056
	252	237	16	18	3	245	7	250	228	173	40	82	27	221	31	226	2056
	5	20	241	239	254	12	242	15	29	84	217	175	230	36	218	39	2056
	251	6	23	233	236	22	255	2	227	30	172	86	169	87	231	26	2056
	14	243	234	24	21	235	10	247	38	219	85	171	88	170	34	223	2056
	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	224	33	35	81	174	32	229	220	2056
	1	256	246	4	19	249	240	13	25	232	222	176	83	225	28	37	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

2584	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	210	43	215	213	212	46	41	48	89	167	96	165	162	94	164	91	2056	
	47	214	42	44	45	211	216	209	168	90	161	92	95	163	93	166	2056	
	49	208	199	58	65	191	190	68	113	143	142	116	146	111	97	160	2056	
	207	50	197	60	192	66	67	189	144	114	115	141	112	145	159	98	2056	
	51	206	59	198	187	69	186	72	117	120	138	139	105	152	99	158	2056	
	205	52	57	200	70	188	71	185	140	137	119	118	151	106	157	100	2056	
	204	53	196	61	73	184	77	180	131	126	121	136	148	109	156	101	2056	
	54	203	62	195	183	74	179	78	125	132	135	122	110	147	102	155	2056	
	202	55	194	63	182	75	178	79	130	127	134	123	149	108	154	103	2056	
	56	201	64	193	76	181	80	177	128	129	124	133	107	150	104	153	2056	
	252	6	3	253	255	1	250	8	226	231	25	32	27	30	228	229	2056	
	5	251	254	4	2	256	7	249	31	26	232	225	230	227	29	28	2056	
	9	248	13	244	17	239	238	20	33	223	222	36	81	176	88	169	2056	
	247	10	243	14	240	18	19	237	224	34	35	221	175	82	170	87	2056	
	12	245	242	15	21	235	234	24	37	219	218	40	174	83	85	172	2056	
	246	11	16	241	236	22	23	233	220	38	39	217	84	173	171	86	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

2731	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	205	52	53	58	211	201	59	189	113	143	115	138	120	118	141	140	2056	
	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	144	114	142	119	137	139	116	117	2056	
	191	66	69	187	186	72	64	193	164	149	104	106	91	157	95	162	2056	
	200	57	188	70	71	185	190	67	93	108	153	151	166	100	154	103	2056	
	215	42	73	183	182	76	61	196	163	94	148	111	145	110	167	90	2056	
	62	195	184	74	75	181	207	50	102	155	109	146	112	147	98	159	2056	
	47	210	77	179	178	80	41	216	160	97	99	165	150	96	105	156	2056	
	60	197	180	78	79	177	203	54	89	168	158	92	107	161	152	101	2056	
	65	45	202	214	51	194	213	44	121	128	123	133	132	126	130	135	2056	
	192	212	55	43	206	63	49	208	136	129	134	124	125	131	127	122	2056	
	25	232	226	31	18	237	16	252	3	245	255	2	175	82	37	220	2056	
	231	26	32	225	239	20	241	5	254	12	242	15	84	173	219	38	2056	
	230	27	227	30	251	6	236	23	233	22	10	247	174	83	218	39	2056	
	28	229	29	228	14	243	21	234	24	235	7	250	81	176	40	217	2056	
	36	222	33	223	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	85	171	88	170	2056	
	221	35	224	34	1	256	246	4	19	249	240	13	172	86	169	87	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

2866	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	119	137	114	142	116	117	139	144	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056
	138	120	143	115	141	140	118	113	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056
	99	158	149	108	109	147	112	146	191	66	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056
	98	159	107	150	148	110	145	111	205	52	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056
	160	97	152	105	153	103	102	156	215	42	73	182	183	76	49	208	2056
	157	100	106	151	104	154	155	101	62	195	184	75	74	181	213	44	2056
	161	163	95	90	93	168	92	166	47	210	77	179	178	80	41	216	2056
	96	94	162	167	164	89	165	91	60	197	180	78	79	177	203	54	2056
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	51	65	202	214	45	194	190	67	2056
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	206	192	55	43	212	63	207	50	2056
	243	31	29	12	227	250	1	15	241	230	13	32	238	237	23	234	2056
	14	226	228	245	30	7	256	242	16	27	244	225	19	20	254	3	2056
	22	235	170	86	83	88	172	81	175	218	173	37	40	219	5	252	2056
	247	10	87	171	174	169	85	176	82	39	84	220	217	38	232	25	2056
	221	36	255	223	9	6	222	253	11	33	18	249	231	21	240	28	2056
	24	233	2	34	248	251	35	4	246	224	239	8	26	236	17	229	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 317 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.7 Part 7: Based on Magic Rectangles of Different Orders

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is also very much similar to parts 3, 4, 5 and 6. See below few examples.

2874	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056
96	161	105	108	151	150	97	160	228	173	40	82	27	221	31	226	2056
89	168	152	149	106	107	104	153	29	84	217	175	230	36	231	26	2056
167	90	113	144	117	140	99	158	227	30	169	86	172	87	218	39	2056
165	92	143	114	139	118	156	101	38	219	88	171	85	170	34	223	2056
164	93	142	115	138	119	157	100	224	33	220	35	174	32	81	229	2056
162	95	116	141	120	137	102	155	25	232	37	222	83	225	176	28	2056
94	163	109	112	147	146	159	98	210	48	43	213	212	46	41	215	2056
91	166	148	145	110	111	154	103	47	209	214	44	45	211	216	42	2056
130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	56	201	65	68	191	190	57	200	2056
127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	49	208	192	189	66	67	64	193	2056
245	237	16	18	3	252	7	250	207	50	73	184	77	180	59	198	2056
12	20	241	239	254	5	242	15	205	52	183	74	179	78	196	61	2056
251	6	22	236	233	23	255	2	204	53	182	75	178	79	197	60	2056
1	256	235	21	24	234	10	247	202	55	76	181	80	177	62	195	2056
248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	54	203	69	72	187	186	199	58	2056
14	243	246	4	19	249	240	13	51	206	188	185	70	71	194	63	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

2995	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056
111	148	110	145	108	149	100	157	228	173	40	82	27	221	218	39	2056
146	109	147	112	150	107	97	160	29	84	217	175	230	36	31	226	2056
101	155	154	104	151	106	159	98	227	30	172	87	169	86	231	26	2056
156	102	103	153	105	152	158	99	38	219	85	170	88	171	34	223	2056
91	165	89	164	167	162	94	96	224	33	32	229	174	35	81	220	2056
166	92	168	93	90	95	163	161	25	232	225	28	83	222	176	37	2056
141	115	113	140	143	118	120	138	210	48	43	213	212	46	41	215	2056
116	142	144	117	114	139	137	119	47	209	214	44	45	211	216	42	2056
130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	79	74	179	182	77	76	184	177	2056
127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	178	183	78	75	180	181	73	80	2056
9	248	13	244	24	233	17	240	55	203	50	53	206	201	208	52	2056
247	10	242	15	234	23	239	18	202	54	207	204	51	56	49	205	2056
12	245	243	14	21	236	238	19	200	57	192	65	62	63	193	196	2056
246	11	16	241	235	22	20	237	58	199	66	191	195	194	64	61	2056
1	250	3	8	6	252	253	255	59	198	67	190	72	69	186	187	2056
256	7	254	249	251	5	4	2	197	60	189	68	185	188	71	70	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

3018	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	119	137	139	114	117	144	142	116	228	173	40	82	27	221	218	39	2056	
	138	120	118	143	140	113	115	141	29	84	217	175	230	36	31	226	2056	
	161	163	95	90	93	168	92	166	227	30	172	87	169	86	231	26	2056	
	96	94	162	167	164	89	165	91	38	219	85	170	88	171	34	223	2056	
	99	158	152	105	153	103	102	156	224	33	32	229	174	35	81	220	2056	
	98	159	106	151	104	154	155	101	25	232	225	28	83	222	176	37	2056	
	160	97	107	150	112	147	109	146	210	48	43	213	212	46	41	215	2056	
	157	100	149	108	145	110	148	111	47	209	214	44	45	211	216	42	2056	
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	70	71	188	185	68	189	60	197	2056	
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	187	186	69	72	190	67	198	59	2056	
	255	1	250	253	6	3	252	8	61	64	194	195	191	66	199	58	2056	
	2	256	7	4	251	254	5	249	196	193	63	62	65	192	57	200	2056	
	9	248	242	15	17	240	21	236	205	49	56	51	204	207	54	202	2056	
	247	10	243	14	239	18	235	22	52	208	201	206	53	50	203	55	2056	
	12	245	13	244	238	19	234	23	80	73	181	180	75	78	183	178	2056	
	246	11	16	241	20	237	24	233	177	184	76	77	182	179	74	79	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

3257	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	157	160	98	99	96	161	138	119	226	231	27	229	228	30	25	32	2056	
	100	97	159	158	94	163	120	137	31	26	230	28	29	227	232	225	2056	
	149	107	106	152	162	95	118	139	37	219	222	36	33	223	218	40	2056	
	108	150	151	105	167	90	143	114	220	38	35	221	224	34	39	217	2056	
	156	102	103	153	164	93	140	117	81	175	174	88	85	171	170	84	2056	
	101	155	154	104	89	168	113	144	176	82	83	169	172	86	87	173	2056	
	146	109	147	112	165	92	115	142	210	48	43	213	212	46	41	215	2056	
	111	148	110	145	91	166	141	116	47	209	214	44	45	211	216	42	2056	
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	177	80	52	205	185	188	71	70	2056	
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	184	73	208	49	72	69	186	187	2056	
	16	247	12	246	9	13	243	242	76	181	201	56	195	194	64	61	2056	
	241	10	245	11	248	244	14	15	77	180	206	51	62	63	193	196	2056	
	17	239	234	24	21	235	238	20	182	75	53	204	65	191	190	68	2056	
	240	18	23	233	236	22	19	237	179	78	50	207	192	66	67	189	2056	
	1	255	3	253	6	252	250	8	74	183	203	54	57	199	198	60	2056	
	256	2	254	4	251	5	7	249	79	178	55	202	200	58	59	197	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

There are total 396 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.8 Part 8: Based on Magic Rectangles of Different Orders

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is also very much similar to parts 3, 4, 5, 7 and 7. See below few examples.

3273	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	146	101	162	145	109	108	155	102	228	173	40	82	27	221	31	226	2056	
	111	156	95	112	148	149	158	99	29	84	217	175	230	36	231	26	2056	
	147	110	140	118	137	119	91	166	227	30	169	86	172	87	218	39	2056	
	153	104	117	139	120	138	105	152	38	219	88	171	85	170	34	223	2056	
	164	93	141	144	115	114	103	154	224	33	220	35	174	32	81	229	2056	
	107	150	116	113	142	143	159	98	25	232	37	222	83	225	176	28	2056	
	94	163	89	167	157	96	97	165	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056	
	106	151	168	90	100	161	160	92	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056	
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	205	52	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056	
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	191	66	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056	
	252	237	16	18	3	245	7	250	215	42	76	182	183	73	49	208	2056	
	5	20	241	239	254	12	242	15	62	195	181	75	74	184	207	50	2056	
	251	6	22	233	236	23	255	2	47	210	178	80	179	77	41	216	2056	
	1	256	235	24	21	234	10	247	60	197	79	177	78	180	190	67	2056	
	248	9	11	253	238	8	17	244	51	65	202	214	45	194	203	54	2056	
	14	243	246	4	19	249	240	13	206	192	55	43	212	63	213	44	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

3413	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	111	148	110	145	108	149	100	157	228	173	40	82	27	221	218	39	2056		
	146	109	147	112	150	107	97	160	29	84	217	175	230	36	34	223	2056		
	101	155	154	104	151	106	159	98	227	30	172	86	169	87	231	26	2056		
	156	102	103	153	105	152	158	99	38	219	85	171	88	170	31	226	2056		
	91	165	89	164	167	162	94	96	224	33	32	229	174	35	81	220	2056		
	166	92	168	93	90	95	163	161	25	232	225	28	83	222	176	37	2056		
	141	115	113	140	143	118	120	138	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056		
	116	142	144	117	114	139	137	119	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056		
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	205	52	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056		
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	191	66	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056		
	255	1	3	253	252	6	250	8	215	42	76	182	183	73	49	208	2056		
	2	256	254	4	5	251	7	249	62	195	181	75	74	184	207	50	2056		
	9	248	13	244	17	240	21	236	47	210	178	80	179	77	41	216	2056		
	247	10	243	14	239	18	235	22	60	197	79	177	78	180	190	67	2056		
	12	245	242	15	238	19	234	23	51	65	202	214	45	194	203	54	2056		
	246	11	16	241	20	237	24	233	206	192	55	43	212	63	213	44	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

3511	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	96	89	167	165	164	162	94	91	226	231	27	229	228	30	25	32	2056		
	161	168	90	92	93	95	163	166	31	26	230	28	29	227	232	225	2056		
	105	152	113	144	117	140	109	148	33	223	222	36	81	176	85	172	2056		
	108	149	143	114	139	118	112	145	224	34	35	221	175	82	171	86	2056		
	151	106	142	115	138	119	147	110	37	219	218	40	174	83	170	87	2056		
	150	107	116	141	120	137	146	111	220	38	39	217	84	173	88	169	2056		
	97	104	99	156	157	102	159	154	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056		
	160	153	158	101	100	155	98	103	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056		
	132	128	123	133	121	126	130	135	205	52	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056		
	125	129	134	124	136	131	127	122	191	66	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056		
	9	248	243	14	21	235	234	24	215	42	76	182	183	73	49	208	2056		
	247	10	242	15	236	22	23	233	62	195	181	75	74	184	207	50	2056		
	12	245	13	244	17	239	238	20	47	210	178	80	179	77	41	216	2056		
	246	11	16	241	240	18	19	237	60	197	79	177	78	180	190	67	2056		
	1	8	3	253	6	252	250	255	51	65	202	214	45	194	203	54	2056		
	256	249	254	4	251	5	7	2	206	192	55	43	212	63	213	44	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

3624	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	92	160	161	100	90	168	151	106	226	231	25	229	228	32	30	27	2056	
	165	97	96	157	167	89	163	94	31	26	232	28	29	225	227	230	2056	
	98	159	143	142	113	116	150	107	33	224	37	220	81	176	85	172	2056	
	154	103	114	115	144	141	93	164	223	34	219	38	175	82	171	86	2056	
	152	105	138	120	139	117	104	153	222	35	218	39	174	83	170	87	2056	
	166	91	119	137	118	140	110	147	36	221	40	217	84	173	88	169	2056	
	99	158	149	148	112	95	156	111	200	57	53	58	211	201	59	189	2056	
	102	155	108	109	145	162	101	146	48	209	204	199	46	56	198	68	2056	
	130	128	123	133	121	126	132	135	205	52	186	187	69	72	64	193	2056	
	127	129	134	124	136	131	125	122	191	66	71	70	188	185	61	196	2056	
	9	248	13	244	21	235	234	24	215	42	76	182	183	73	49	208	2056	
	247	10	242	15	236	22	23	233	62	195	181	75	74	184	207	50	2056	
	12	245	243	14	17	239	238	20	47	210	178	80	179	77	41	216	2056	
	246	11	16	241	240	18	19	237	60	197	79	177	78	180	190	67	2056	
	1	250	3	8	6	252	253	255	51	65	202	214	45	194	203	54	2056	
	256	7	254	249	251	5	4	2	206	192	55	43	212	63	213	44	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

There are total 414 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.9 Part 9: Magic Rectangles of Order 8x16

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is based on magic rectangles of Order 8×16 and different combinations of magic squares of Order 8. See below few examples.

3899	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA												2056			
245	11	10	248	255	2	226	31	193	64	222	35	204	201	55	54	2056	
12	246	247	9	6	251	231	26	198	59	39	218	53	56	202	203	2056	
237	19	18	240	253	4	30	227	60	197	217	40	48	45	211	210	2056	
20	238	239	17	252	5	25	232	61	196	224	33	209	212	46	47	2056	
15	14	244	241	1	256	228	29	200	57	37	220	49	207	206	52	2056	
242	243	13	16	8	249	229	28	195	62	36	221	208	50	51	205	2056	
235	234	24	21	250	7	27	230	58	199	219	38	41	215	214	44	2056	
22	23	233	236	3	254	32	225	63	194	34	223	216	42	43	213	2056	
113	143	142	116	107	150	167	166	92	89	65	192	73	183	182	76	2056	
144	114	115	141	151	106	90	91	165	168	67	190	184	74	75	181	2056	
117	139	138	120	112	145	93	163	162	96	191	66	77	179	178	80	2056	
140	118	119	137	105	152	164	94	95	161	186	71	180	78	79	177	2056	
130	127	121	136	148	109	97	159	158	100	188	69	84	173	85	172	2056	
128	129	135	122	110	147	160	98	99	157	70	187	174	83	171	86	2056	
131	126	134	123	146	111	101	155	154	104	189	68	81	176	170	87	2056	
125	132	124	133	149	108	156	102	103	153	72	185	175	82	88	169	2056	
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4026	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA												2056			
31	226	2	255	248	10	11	245	213	43	42	216	223	34	194	63	2056	
26	231	251	6	9	247	246	12	44	214	215	41	38	219	199	58	2056	
227	30	4	253	240	18	19	237	205	51	50	208	221	36	62	195	2056	
232	25	5	252	17	239	238	20	52	206	207	49	220	37	57	200	2056	
29	228	256	1	241	16	21	236	204	53	48	209	33	224	196	61	2056	
28	229	249	8	244	13	24	233	201	56	45	212	40	217	197	60	2056	
230	27	7	250	14	243	234	23	55	202	211	46	218	39	59	198	2056	
225	32	254	3	15	242	235	22	54	203	210	47	35	222	64	193	2056	
148	109	147	118	144	105	166	167	92	89	188	69	187	78	184	65	2056	
133	124	110	139	113	152	91	90	165	168	82	175	70	179	73	192	2056	
120	137	126	131	115	142	93	163	162	96	181	76	172	85	75	182	2056	
122	135	129	128	149	108	164	94	95	161	173	84	86	171	189	68	2056	
107	150	127	130	134	123	97	159	158	100	67	190	169	88	180	77	2056	
141	116	132	125	112	145	160	98	99	157	80	177	87	170	72	185	2056	
151	111	138	114	121	136	101	155	154	104	71	178	191	74	81	176	2056	
106	146	119	143	140	117	156	102	103	153	186	79	66	183	174	83	2056	
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4051	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	26	232	227	28	225	230	31	29	33	224	43	214	54	203	57	200	2056	
	231	25	30	229	32	27	226	228	35	222	215	42	205	52	64	193	2056	
	253	254	2	250	1	11	14	243	223	34	41	216	49	208	194	63	2056	
	4	3	255	7	256	246	13	244	221	36	48	209	204	53	197	60	2056	
	248	9	23	236	233	22	240	17	220	37	210	47	202	55	199	58	2056	
	5	252	234	21	24	235	247	10	218	39	46	211	56	201	62	195	2056	
	241	16	238	15	245	18	249	6	38	219	212	45	207	50	59	198	2056	
	20	237	19	242	12	239	8	251	40	217	213	44	51	206	196	61	2056	
	174	100	179	176	181	186	69	72	98	165	73	93	66	167	65	192	2056	
	83	157	78	81	76	71	188	185	159	92	184	164	191	90	171	86	2056	
	155	102	149	151	107	105	148	147	111	112	113	141	115	143	166	91	2056	
	168	89	108	106	150	152	109	110	146	145	144	116	142	114	94	163	2056	
	77	180	117	124	119	137	136	135	123	139	125	127	131	129	103	154	2056	
	187	70	140	133	138	120	121	122	134	118	132	130	126	128	172	85	2056	
	96	161	97	170	74	158	156	175	104	95	189	75	67	178	177	84	2056	
	88	169	160	87	183	99	101	82	153	162	68	182	190	79	80	173	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

4125	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	8	1	255	253	252	250	6	3	52	209	37	216	36	221	199	58	2056	
	249	256	2	4	5	7	251	254	205	48	220	41	35	222	57	200	2056	
	17	240	25	232	29	228	21	236	51	206	202	55	223	34	62	195	2056	
	20	237	231	26	227	30	24	233	210	47	53	204	39	218	197	60	2056	
	239	18	230	27	226	31	235	22	44	213	56	201	224	33	59	198	2056	
	238	19	28	229	32	225	234	23	207	50	203	54	214	43	64	193	2056	
	9	16	11	244	245	14	247	242	40	217	215	208	45	46	194	63	2056	
	248	241	246	13	12	243	10	15	219	38	42	49	212	211	196	61	2056	
	113	143	142	116	105	152	191	66	183	80	75	181	180	78	178	73	2056	
	144	114	115	141	151	106	186	71	74	177	182	76	77	179	79	184	2056	
	117	139	138	120	112	145	67	190	83	175	81	173	172	86	170	88	2056	
	140	118	119	137	107	150	65	192	174	82	176	84	85	171	87	169	2056	
	125	130	131	128	148	109	188	69	89	168	93	164	97	159	158	100	2056	
	132	127	126	129	110	147	70	187	167	90	163	94	160	98	99	157	2056	
	121	134	135	124	146	111	189	68	166	91	162	95	101	154	155	104	2056	
	136	123	122	133	149	108	72	185	92	165	96	161	156	103	102	153	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

There are total 512 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.10 Part 10: Magic Rectangles of Order 8x16

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is based on magic rectangles of Order 8×16 . See below few examples

4193	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	29	36	243	240	245	5	8	250	9	231	238	34	2	229	230	27	2056
	228	221	14	17	12	252	249	7	248	26	19	223	255	28	235	22	2056
	219	38	213	41	205	215	212	211	47	48	43	207	49	51	236	21	2056
	232	25	44	216	52	42	45	46	210	209	214	50	208	206	30	227	2056
	32	225	53	203	55	201	200	199	59	60	61	63	195	193	39	218	2056
	251	6	204	54	202	56	57	58	198	197	196	194	62	64	1	256	2056
	24	233	33	234	10	222	220	239	40	31	253	11	3	241	242	20	2056
	13	244	224	23	247	35	37	18	217	226	4	246	254	16	15	237	2056
	174	100	179	176	181	72	98	186	73	167	69	93	66	165	65	192	2056
	83	157	78	81	76	185	159	71	184	90	188	164	191	92	171	86	2056
	155	102	150	107	146	111	113	144	117	140	134	123	125	132	166	91	2056
	168	89	108	149	112	145	143	114	139	118	135	122	131	126	94	163	2056
	77	180	151	106	147	110	142	115	138	119	121	136	130	127	103	154	2056
	187	70	105	152	109	148	116	141	120	137	124	133	128	129	172	85	2056
	96	161	97	170	74	158	156	175	104	95	189	75	67	178	177	84	2056
	88	169	160	87	183	99	101	82	153	162	68	182	190	79	80	173	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4213	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	61	203	55	201	200	199	59	60	53	195	63	193	37	220	33	224	2056
	196	54	202	56	57	58	198	197	204	62	194	64	219	38	223	34	2056
	41	215	213	43	212	211	47	48	49	207	51	205	218	39	222	35	2056
	216	42	44	214	45	46	210	209	208	50	206	52	40	217	36	221	2056
	27	229	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	17	239	228	30	226	32	2056
	230	28	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	240	18	29	227	31	225	2056
	1	255	3	253	252	6	8	250	245	11	247	9	244	14	242	16	2056
	256	2	254	4	5	251	249	7	12	246	10	248	13	243	15	241	2056
	148	109	147	118	144	105	166	167	92	89	188	69	187	78	184	65	2056
	133	124	110	139	113	152	91	90	165	168	82	175	70	179	73	192	2056
	120	137	126	131	115	142	93	163	162	96	181	76	172	85	75	182	2056
	122	135	129	128	149	108	164	94	95	161	173	84	86	171	189	68	2056
	107	150	127	130	134	123	97	159	158	100	67	190	169	88	180	77	2056
	141	116	132	125	112	145	160	98	99	157	80	177	87	170	72	185	2056
	151	111	138	114	121	136	101	155	154	104	71	178	191	74	81	176	2056
	106	146	119	143	140	117	156	102	103	153	186	79	66	183	174	83	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4259	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	40	218	37	219	29	228	25	232	9	248	41	216	49	207	206	52	2056
	217	39	220	38	227	30	231	26	247	10	215	42	208	50	51	205	2056
	33	223	222	36	226	31	230	27	11	246	43	214	53	203	202	56	2056
	224	34	35	221	32	225	28	229	245	12	213	44	204	54	55	201	2056
	17	239	236	237	19	22	234	24	244	13	46	211	57	199	198	60	2056
	240	18	21	20	238	235	23	233	242	15	48	209	200	58	59	197	2056
	1	8	3	253	252	6	250	255	14	243	210	47	61	195	194	64	2056
	256	249	254	4	5	251	7	2	16	241	212	45	196	62	63	193	2056
	87	175	83	173	172	171	81	89	88	167	91	165	180	77	65	192	2056
	170	82	174	84	85	86	176	168	169	90	166	92	183	74	186	71	2056
	93	163	95	160	161	159	99	100	101	155	103	153	75	182	72	185	2056
	164	94	162	97	96	98	158	157	156	102	154	104	181	76	189	68	2056
	113	143	138	118	140	115	141	120	109	148	105	152	78	179	188	69	2056
	144	114	119	139	117	142	116	137	147	110	151	106	73	184	70	187	2056
	121	135	123	133	132	126	130	128	146	111	150	107	178	79	191	66	2056
	136	122	134	124	125	131	127	129	112	145	108	149	80	177	67	190	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4429	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				@IJTANEJA	2056						
12	246	9	247	1	256	25	231	230	28	41	216	49	207	206	52	2056	
245	11	248	10	252	5	232	26	27	229	215	42	208	50	51	205	2056	
242	16	243	13	3	254	29	227	226	32	43	214	53	202	203	56	2056	
15	241	14	244	253	4	228	30	31	225	213	44	204	55	54	201	2056	
17	239	238	20	255	2	33	223	222	36	46	211	57	199	198	60	2056	
240	18	19	237	250	7	224	34	35	221	48	209	200	58	59	197	2056	
21	235	234	24	6	251	218	219	37	40	210	47	61	195	194	64	2056	
236	22	23	233	8	249	39	38	220	217	212	45	196	62	63	193	2056	
113	143	142	116	107	150	167	166	92	89	65	192	73	183	182	76	2056	
144	114	115	141	151	106	90	91	165	168	67	190	184	74	75	181	2056	
117	139	138	120	112	145	93	163	162	96	191	66	77	179	178	80	2056	
140	118	119	137	105	152	164	94	95	161	186	71	180	78	79	177	2056	
130	128	131	125	148	109	97	159	158	100	188	69	84	174	81	175	2056	
127	129	126	132	110	147	160	98	99	157	70	187	173	83	176	82	2056	
121	135	134	124	146	111	101	155	154	104	189	68	85	171	170	88	2056	
136	122	123	133	149	108	156	102	103	153	72	185	172	86	87	169	2056	
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 246 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.11 Part 11: Different Combinations of Magic Squares of Order 8

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. It is based on different combinations of magic squares of order 8.

4537	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	31	26	227	232	29	28	230	225	40	217	49	52	207	206	41	216	2056	
	226	231	30	25	228	229	27	32	33	224	208	205	50	51	48	209	2056	
	2	251	4	5	256	249	7	254	223	34	57	200	61	196	43	214	2056	
	255	6	253	252	1	8	250	3	221	36	199	58	195	62	212	45	2056	
	248	9	240	17	241	16	21	236	220	37	198	59	194	63	213	44	2056	
	10	247	18	239	244	13	24	233	218	39	60	197	64	193	46	211	2056	
	11	246	19	238	14	243	234	23	38	219	53	56	203	202	215	42	2056	
	245	12	237	20	15	242	235	22	35	222	204	201	54	55	210	47	2056	
	104	153	113	116	143	142	105	152	86	171	178	79	84	173	76	181	2056	
	97	160	144	141	114	115	112	145	87	170	179	78	174	83	182	75	2056	
	159	98	121	136	125	132	107	150	169	88	77	180	175	82	183	74	2056	
	157	100	135	122	131	126	148	109	172	85	80	177	81	176	73	184	2056	
	156	101	134	123	130	127	149	108	67	186	72	65	188	189	70	191	2056	
	154	103	124	133	128	129	110	147	190	71	185	192	69	68	187	66	2056	
	102	155	117	120	139	138	151	106	96	91	165	164	89	94	167	162	2056	
	99	158	140	137	118	119	146	111	161	166	92	93	168	163	90	95	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

4556	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	20	241	5	248	4	253	231	26	44	217	216	36	34	224	219	38	2056	
	237	16	252	9	3	254	25	232	213	40	41	221	223	33	207	50	2056	
	19	238	234	23	255	2	30	227	43	214	199	57	60	198	206	51	2056	
	242	15	21	236	7	250	229	28	210	47	58	200	197	59	37	220	2056	
	12	245	24	233	256	1	32	225	208	49	194	64	61	195	48	209	2056	
	239	18	235	22	246	11	27	230	222	35	63	193	196	62	54	203	2056	
	8	249	247	240	13	14	226	31	42	215	205	212	56	55	204	39	2056	
	251	6	10	17	244	243	228	29	46	211	52	45	201	202	53	218	2056	
	108	153	152	100	98	160	142	115	93	164	179	180	81	74	70	187	2056	
	149	104	105	157	159	97	155	102	95	162	78	77	176	183	185	72	2056	
	110	147	135	121	134	124	143	114	161	96	75	182	86	171	82	175	2056	
	146	111	122	136	123	133	101	156	166	91	65	192	169	88	181	76	2056	
	144	113	130	128	125	131	112	145	92	165	186	71	172	85	79	178	2056	
	158	99	127	129	132	126	118	139	163	94	66	191	87	170	174	83	2056	
	107	150	141	148	120	119	140	103	168	89	190	67	73	188	80	173	2056	
	106	151	116	109	137	138	117	154	90	167	189	68	184	69	177	84	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

4585	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	225	230	28	29	232	227	26	31	219	40	207	44	210	51	205	52	2056		
	32	27	229	228	25	30	231	226	38	217	50	213	47	206	48	209	2056		
	254	7	249	256	5	4	251	2	42	215	203	56	53	202	220	37	2056		
	3	250	8	1	252	253	6	255	49	208	54	201	204	55	41	216	2056		
	15	14	244	241	17	240	9	248	212	45	214	224	39	223	35	36	2056		
	242	243	13	16	239	18	247	10	211	46	43	33	218	34	222	221	2056		
	235	234	24	21	238	19	246	11	196	194	64	59	197	62	57	199	2056		
	22	23	233	236	20	237	12	245	61	63	193	198	60	195	200	58	2056		
	122	136	131	127	124	134	129	125	181	76	173	84	172	169	87	86	2056		
	135	121	126	130	133	123	128	132	75	182	83	174	85	88	170	171	2056		
	157	107	98	154	97	158	110	147	74	183	82	175	80	77	179	178	2056		
	100	150	159	103	160	99	109	148	184	73	176	81	177	180	78	79	2056		
	101	156	140	119	137	118	144	113	191	70	189	188	65	72	186	67	2056		
	145	112	117	138	120	139	151	106	66	187	68	69	192	185	71	190	2056		
	152	105	142	111	149	114	153	102	162	167	94	89	164	165	91	96	2056		
	116	141	115	146	108	143	104	155	95	90	163	168	93	92	166	161	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056		

4822	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								@IJTANEJA	2056
	22	235	242	15	20	237	12	245	193	198	60	61	200	195	58	63	2056		
	23	234	243	14	238	19	246	11	64	59	197	196	57	62	199	194	2056		
	233	24	13	244	239	18	247	10	222	39	217	224	37	36	219	34	2056		
	236	21	16	241	17	240	9	248	35	218	40	33	220	221	38	223	2056		
	3	250	8	1	252	253	6	255	47	46	212	209	49	208	41	216	2056		
	254	7	249	256	5	4	251	2	210	211	45	48	207	50	215	42	2056		
	32	27	229	228	25	30	231	226	203	202	56	53	206	51	214	43	2056		
	225	230	28	29	232	227	26	31	54	55	201	204	52	205	44	213	2056		
	149	108	141	116	137	119	140	118	95	90	163	168	93	92	166	161	2056		
	107	150	115	142	120	138	117	139	162	167	94	89	164	165	91	96	2056		
	106	151	114	143	112	146	147	109	66	187	68	69	192	185	71	190	2056		
	152	105	144	113	145	111	110	148	191	70	189	188	65	72	186	67	2056		
	104	102	154	156	157	159	97	99	184	73	176	81	177	80	85	172	2056		
	153	155	103	101	100	98	160	158	74	183	82	175	180	77	88	169	2056		
	135	121	126	130	132	128	123	133	75	182	83	174	78	179	170	87	2056		
	122	136	131	127	125	129	134	124	181	76	173	84	79	178	171	86	2056		
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056		

There are total 484 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.12 Part 12: Centered With Striped Magic Square of Orders 4 and 8

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16 constructed in a such a way that there is a striped magic square of orders 4 and 8 are at the middle of magic squares of order 16. Below are few examples.

4923	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	9	248	13	244	17	240	21	236	142	115	25	232	222	223	33	36	2056	
	246	11	242	15	239	18	235	22	155	102	231	26	35	34	224	221	2056	
	247	10	243	14	238	19	234	23	143	114	27	230	37	40	218	219	2056	
	12	245	16	241	20	237	24	233	101	156	229	28	220	217	39	38	2056	
	1	255	3	253	252	6	250	8	112	145	226	31	41	215	214	44	2056	
	256	2	254	4	5	251	7	249	118	139	32	225	216	42	43	213	2056	
	141	148	120	119	140	103	135	122	134	123	228	29	45	211	210	48	2056	
	116	109	137	138	117	154	128	129	125	132	30	227	212	46	47	209	2056	
	81	175	174	84	75	182	121	136	124	133	108	153	152	100	98	160	2056	
	176	82	83	173	181	76	130	127	131	126	149	104	105	157	159	97	2056	
	85	171	170	88	73	184	110	147	205	207	51	49	204	54	202	56	2056	
	172	86	87	169	183	74	146	111	52	50	206	208	53	203	55	201	2056	
	89	166	92	167	180	77	144	113	57	200	61	196	68	189	69	188	2056	
	168	91	165	90	78	179	158	99	199	58	195	62	191	66	186	71	2056	
	93	96	162	163	178	79	107	150	198	59	194	63	65	192	72	185	2056	
	164	161	95	94	80	177	106	151	60	197	64	193	190	67	187	70	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

4936	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	4	253	5	251	7	249	248	10	246	12	93	164	234	24	235	21	2056
	255	2	252	6	250	8	9	247	11	245	95	162	23	233	22	236	2056
	254	3	241	243	15	13	240	18	238	20	197	60	35	222	25	232	2056
	1	256	16	14	242	244	17	239	19	237	79	178	223	34	231	26	2056
	173	72	59	184	88	68	92	186	193	170	81	176	33	224	27	230	2056
	84	185	198	73	169	189	165	71	64	87	181	76	221	36	229	28	2056
	105	152	113	144	166	91	135	122	134	123	183	74	220	37	228	29	2056
	151	106	143	114	182	75	128	129	125	132	200	57	38	219	30	227	2056
	107	150	115	142	85	172	121	136	124	133	94	163	218	39	226	31	2056
	149	108	141	116	187	70	130	127	131	126	82	175	40	217	32	225	2056
	148	109	140	117	199	58	86	192	194	195	96	78	80	83	90	191	2056
	110	147	118	139	89	168	171	65	63	62	161	179	177	174	167	66	2056
	146	111	138	119	180	77	207	56	51	205	204	54	202	49	158	99	2056
	112	145	120	137	61	196	50	201	206	52	53	203	55	208	100	157	2056
	101	155	154	104	69	188	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	159	98	2056
	156	102	103	153	67	190	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	97	160	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4946	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	191	66	190	67	1	255	3	253	252	6	250	8	183	80	73	178	2056
	72	185	69	188	256	2	254	4	5	251	7	249	74	177	184	79	2056
	65	192	68	189	9	247	11	245	244	14	242	16	182	77	76	179	2056
	186	71	187	70	248	10	246	12	13	243	15	241	75	180	181	78	2056
	49	208	57	200	108	150	151	105	104	154	155	101	17	240	25	232	2056
	207	50	199	58	149	107	106	152	153	103	102	156	239	18	231	26	2056
	51	206	59	198	97	159	158	100	109	147	146	112	19	238	27	230	2056
	205	52	197	60	160	98	99	157	148	110	111	145	237	20	229	28	2056
	204	53	196	61	121	135	134	124	120	138	139	117	236	21	228	29	2056
	54	203	62	195	136	122	123	133	137	119	118	140	22	235	30	227	2056
	202	55	194	63	116	142	143	113	125	131	130	128	234	23	226	31	2056
	56	201	64	193	141	115	114	144	132	126	127	129	24	233	32	225	2056
	167	96	89	162	33	223	35	221	220	38	218	40	175	82	174	83	2056
	90	161	168	95	224	34	222	36	37	219	39	217	88	169	85	172	2056
	166	93	92	163	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	81	176	84	173	2056
	91	164	165	94	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	170	87	171	86	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4972	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	167	90	1	255	3	253	252	6	250	8	190	67	73	80	183	178	2056
	89	168	256	2	254	4	5	251	7	249	69	188	184	177	74	79	2056
	96	161	14	11	16	245	244	9	242	247	68	189	24	233	25	232	2056
	162	95	243	246	241	12	13	248	15	10	187	70	234	23	231	26	2056
	191	72	65	186	118	139	109	148	116	141	108	149	19	238	27	230	2056
	66	185	192	71	140	117	147	110	142	115	150	107	237	20	229	28	2056
	49	208	57	200	119	138	146	111	143	114	151	106	236	21	228	29	2056
	207	50	199	58	137	120	112	145	113	144	105	152	22	235	30	227	2056
	51	206	59	198	99	97	159	157	156	154	102	104	239	18	226	31	2056
	205	52	197	60	158	160	98	100	101	103	155	153	17	240	32	225	2056
	204	53	194	63	133	123	128	132	130	126	121	135	182	77	76	179	2056
	54	203	62	195	124	134	129	125	127	131	136	122	75	180	181	78	2056
	202	55	196	61	175	82	38	223	33	221	220	218	40	35	84	173	2056
	56	201	64	193	88	169	219	34	224	36	37	39	217	222	174	83	2056
	166	93	92	163	81	176	41	215	43	213	212	46	210	48	85	172	2056
	91	164	165	94	170	87	216	42	214	44	45	211	47	209	171	86	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 60 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.13 Part 13: Centered With Striped Magic Square of Order 12

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16 constructed in a such a way that there is a striped magic square of order 12 at the middle of magic squares of order 16. Below are few examples.

5051	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	254	255	1	4	5	251	250	8	9	247	246	12	242	243	13	16	2056
	3	2	256	253	252	6	7	249	248	10	11	245	15	14	244	241	2056
	53	204	64	75	186	183	195	68	65	192	105	152	113	144	17	240	2056
	203	54	193	182	71	74	62	189	72	185	151	106	116	141	239	18	2056
	202	55	66	191	179	80	178	77	181	76	150	107	142	115	238	19	2056
	56	201	73	184	78	177	79	180	196	61	108	149	143	114	20	237	2056
	49	208	188	69	59	63	60	199	190	200	109	147	146	112	21	236	2056
	207	50	187	70	198	194	197	58	67	57	148	110	111	145	235	22	2056
	206	51	121	135	134	124	159	162	92	171	88	99	89	168	234	23	2056
	52	205	136	122	123	133	98	95	165	86	169	158	96	161	24	233	2056
	45	212	128	129	117	140	90	167	154	101	155	104	157	100	25	232	2056
	211	46	131	126	138	119	97	160	103	156	102	153	172	85	231	26	2056
	210	47	125	132	139	118	164	93	83	176	84	175	166	87	230	27	2056
	48	209	130	127	120	137	163	94	174	81	173	82	91	170	28	229	2056
	44	41	214	215	37	219	218	40	33	223	222	36	29	32	227	226	2056
	213	216	43	42	220	38	39	217	224	34	35	221	228	225	30	31	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

5108	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	247	256	15	38	11	228	232	36	2	13	218	211	53	239	234	23	2056
	10	1	242	219	246	29	25	221	255	244	39	46	204	18	7	250	2056
	43	214	173	72	59	88	184	68	92	186	193	170	93	164	216	41	2056
	8	249	84	185	198	169	73	189	165	71	64	87	95	162	12	245	2056
	210	47	166	91	149	108	141	116	137	119	140	118	197	60	3	254	2056
	222	35	182	75	107	150	115	142	120	138	117	139	79	178	252	5	2056
	33	224	85	172	106	151	114	143	112	146	147	109	81	176	240	17	2056
	26	231	187	70	152	105	144	113	145	111	110	148	82	175	16	241	2056
	207	50	199	58	104	102	154	156	157	159	97	99	183	74	54	203	2056
	56	201	89	168	153	155	103	101	100	98	160	158	200	57	51	206	2056
	236	21	180	77	135	121	126	130	132	128	123	133	94	163	209	48	2056
	30	227	61	196	122	136	131	127	125	129	134	124	181	76	213	44	2056
	205	52	69	188	78	192	194	96	195	86	80	83	90	191	55	202	2056
	248	9	67	190	179	65	63	161	62	171	177	174	167	66	237	20	2056
	24	233	27	253	225	235	31	45	34	19	14	220	229	42	217	208	2056
	251	6	230	4	32	22	226	212	223	238	243	37	28	215	40	49	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

5136	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	254	255	1	4	5	251	250	8	9	247	246	12	242	243	13	16	2056
	3	2	256	253	252	6	7	249	248	10	11	245	15	14	244	241	2056
	53	204	104	97	159	157	156	154	102	99	57	200	191	66	17	240	2056
	203	54	153	160	98	100	101	103	155	158	199	58	70	187	239	18	2056
	202	55	113	144	121	136	125	132	139	118	196	61	67	190	238	19	2056
	56	201	116	141	135	122	131	126	138	119	197	60	189	68	20	237	2056
	49	208	143	114	134	123	130	127	117	140	59	198	188	69	21	236	2056
	207	50	142	115	124	133	128	129	120	137	62	195	65	192	235	22	2056
	206	51	105	112	149	148	107	110	151	146	194	63	186	71	234	23	2056
	52	205	152	145	108	109	150	147	106	111	64	193	72	185	24	233	2056
	45	212	73	183	75	181	180	179	79	80	173	175	81	83	25	232	2056
	211	46	184	74	182	76	77	78	178	177	84	82	176	174	231	26	2056
	210	47	161	169	91	95	168	167	171	92	93	163	87	85	230	27	2056
	48	209	96	88	166	162	89	90	86	165	164	94	170	172	28	229	2056
	44	41	214	215	37	219	218	40	33	223	222	36	29	32	227	226	2056
	213	216	43	42	220	38	39	217	224	34	35	221	228	225	30	31	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

5166	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	247	256	15	38	11	228	232	36	2	13	218	211	53	239	234	23	2056
	10	1	242	219	246	29	25	221	255	244	39	46	204	18	7	250	2056
	43	214	125	132	147	148	113	106	111	146	175	82	89	168	216	41	2056
	8	249	129	128	110	109	144	151	142	115	81	176	166	91	12	245	2056
	210	47	134	123	158	99	118	139	114	143	174	83	92	165	3	254	2056
	222	35	124	133	97	160	137	120	149	108	84	173	167	90	252	5	2056
	33	224	127	130	154	103	119	138	102	155	85	171	170	88	240	17	2056
	26	231	131	126	98	159	140	117	153	104	172	86	87	169	16	241	2056
	207	50	136	121	107	150	156	112	105	141	73	183	182	76	54	203	2056
	56	201	122	135	157	100	101	145	152	116	184	74	75	181	51	206	2056
	236	21	198	199	57	60	61	196	93	164	186	71	77	180	209	48	2056
	30	227	59	58	200	197	64	193	96	161	187	70	80	177	213	44	2056
	205	52	65	68	190	191	194	63	162	95	69	188	179	78	55	202	2056
	248	9	192	189	67	66	195	62	163	94	72	185	178	79	237	20	2056
	24	233	27	253	225	235	31	45	34	19	14	220	229	42	217	208	2056
	251	6	230	4	32	22	226	212	223	238	243	37	28	215	40	49	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 220 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author's site [97].

2.14 Part 14: $(a + b)^2$ - Type Striped Magic Squares

This part brings some **striped magic squares** of order 16. These are made by using the algebraic formula $colorblue(a + b)^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab$, $colorbluea = 12, b = 4, ab = 12 \times 4$ and $colorblueba = 4 \times 12$. See below few examples.

5207	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA																2056
	57	199	67	189	196	195	63	64	65	191	197	59	52	206	207	49	2056	
	200	58	190	68	61	62	194	193	192	66	60	198	205	51	50	208	2056	
	95	162	83	107	102	176	152	156	98	154	85	172	56	202	203	53	2056	
	108	149	174	150	155	81	105	101	159	103	94	163	201	55	54	204	2056	
	160	97	113	144	117	140	121	136	125	132	148	109	44	214	215	41	2056	
	96	161	143	114	139	118	135	122	131	126	173	84	213	43	42	216	2056	
	91	166	142	115	138	119	134	123	130	127	93	164	45	211	210	48	2056	
	146	111	116	141	120	137	124	133	128	129	112	145	212	46	47	209	2056	
	167	90	99	82	110	171	157	151	169	89	170	87	33	223	222	36	2056	
	165	92	158	175	147	86	100	106	88	168	153	104	224	34	35	221	2056	
	76	179	71	185	184	187	69	75	77	183	177	79	40	218	219	37	2056	
	181	78	186	72	73	70	188	182	180	74	80	178	217	39	38	220	2056	
	1	256	8	249	12	245	13	244	20	237	29	228	235	22	234	23	2056	
	255	2	250	7	246	11	243	14	238	19	227	30	28	229	25	232	2056	
	254	3	251	6	247	10	242	15	239	18	226	31	21	236	24	233	2056	
	4	253	5	252	9	248	16	241	17	240	32	225	230	27	231	26	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	

5230	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	74	166	77	192	171	75	195	190	61	84	90	167	52	206	207	49	2056
	183	91	180	65	86	182	62	67	196	173	191	66	205	51	50	208	2056
	73	184	97	163	106	153	159	93	158	99	57	200	56	203	202	53	2056
	70	187	160	94	151	104	98	164	95	162	81	176	201	54	55	204	2056
	68	189	107	150	142	116	113	143	109	148	172	85	44	214	215	41	2056
	169	88	101	156	115	141	144	114	152	105	198	59	213	43	42	216	2056
	170	87	149	108	111	145	155	154	110	96	168	89	45	211	210	48	2056
	82	175	157	100	146	112	102	103	147	161	71	186	212	46	47	209	2056
	197	60	165	72	179	79	83	80	181	64	194	188	33	223	222	36	2056
	199	58	92	185	78	178	174	177	76	193	63	69	224	34	35	221	2056
	130	121	135	120	128	138	134	124	125	139	131	117	40	218	219	37	2056
	127	136	122	137	129	119	123	133	132	118	126	140	217	39	38	220	2056
	1	256	8	249	12	245	13	244	20	237	29	228	235	22	234	23	2056
	255	2	250	7	246	11	243	14	238	19	227	30	28	229	25	232	2056
	254	3	251	6	247	10	242	15	239	18	226	31	21	236	24	233	2056
	4	253	5	252	9	248	16	241	17	240	32	225	230	27	231	26	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

5437	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA														2056	
	181	76	165	92	125	134	131	127	122	136	129	124	35	222	45	212	2056
	75	182	90	167	132	123	126	130	135	121	128	133	221	36	55	202	2056
	74	183	91	166	103	155	153	101	100	98	160	158	33	224	47	210	2056
	184	73	168	89	154	102	104	156	157	159	97	99	223	34	209	48	2056
	185	72	161	96	106	151	144	113	145	111	110	148	220	37	211	46	2056
	71	186	95	162	107	150	114	143	112	146	147	109	219	38	207	50	2056
	70	187	94	163	152	105	115	142	138	120	117	139	39	218	51	206	2056
	188	69	164	93	149	108	141	116	119	137	140	118	40	217	52	205	2056
	60	199	57	198	61	195	191	64	65	68	194	190	41	216	53	204	2056
	197	58	200	59	196	62	66	193	192	189	63	67	215	42	203	54	2056
	178	77	175	85	170	88	171	84	174	179	81	80	43	214	208	49	2056
	79	180	82	172	87	169	86	173	83	78	176	177	213	44	201	56	2056
	1	255	247	9	252	251	7	8	11	253	3	245	231	32	25	226	2056
	256	2	10	248	5	6	250	249	246	4	254	12	26	225	232	31	2056
	13	240	15	241	239	233	19	20	21	235	23	243	230	29	28	227	2056
	244	17	242	16	18	24	238	237	236	22	234	14	27	228	229	30	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

5590	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ @IJTANEJA												2056			
	118	140	119	137	116	141	108	149	57	200	191	66	43	214	45	212	2056
	139	117	138	120	142	115	150	107	199	58	70	187	220	37	52	205	2056
	109	147	146	112	143	114	151	106	196	61	67	190	35	222	47	210	2056
	148	110	111	145	113	144	105	152	197	60	189	68	41	216	209	48	2056
	99	97	159	157	156	154	102	104	59	198	188	69	221	36	211	46	2056
	158	160	98	100	101	103	155	153	62	195	65	192	219	38	207	50	2056
	133	123	128	132	126	130	121	135	194	63	186	71	39	218	51	206	2056
	124	134	129	125	131	127	136	122	64	193	72	185	40	217	53	204	2056
	73	183	75	181	180	179	79	80	173	175	81	83	213	44	55	202	2056
	184	74	182	76	77	78	178	177	84	82	176	174	223	34	203	54	2056
	161	169	91	95	168	167	171	92	93	163	87	85	33	224	208	49	2056
	96	88	166	162	89	90	86	165	164	94	170	172	215	42	201	56	2056
	247	255	1	11	252	251	7	8	9	253	3	245	231	26	230	27	2056
	10	2	256	246	5	6	250	249	248	4	254	12	32	225	29	228	2056
	13	243	15	241	240	239	19	20	21	235	23	233	25	232	28	229	2056
	244	14	242	16	17	18	238	237	236	22	234	24	226	31	227	30	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 440 **striped magic squares** in this part. The complete work is given as **pdf file** in author’s site [97].

3 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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